

Academic Review of Social Psychology and Policy Connections

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Abstract

The fundamental focus of the academic subject that is known as political psychology is the investigation of the ways in which social psychology may be applied to the study of political processes. On page 3, Sears, Huddy, and Jervis (2003) provide a description of political psychology as "the application of what is known about human psychology to the study of politics."

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This definition describes political psychology as "the study of how human psychology is applied to the study of politics." When it comes to the research that has been conducted in the discipline of political science, the branch of psychology known as social psychology has shown to be a far more useful starting place than any of the other subfields of psychology. The discoveries of social psychology have really been tremendously useful in the study of both the political conduct of political leaders and the political behavior of the general population. This has led to the study of a wide range of themes, including political socialization, public opinion, voting behavior, collective political action, ideology, prejudice, political campaigns, presidential performance, policy making, conflict resolution, terrorism, and genocide (see Jost and Sidanius, 2004). There have been initiatives made to modify unfavorable political attitudes and political conduct, such as racial prejudice, low voter participation, and political violence. These efforts depend on a variety of ideas into these topics in order to be successful. The obedience test that Stanley Milgram conducted in 1974 is a well-known illustration of this phenomenon. There is no connection between politics and a learning experiment in which participants are instructed to provide high-voltage electric shocks to other individuals. Emerging basic concepts, such as obedience by the majority of people when asked by an authority (experimenter in this example), are key to understanding political behavior, such as the devotion of public employees to political leaders. This is because political conduct is a product of the interactions between individuals. These realizations assist explain how the heinous atrocities that took place during the Holocaust, for example, may have taken place. The second kind of research is made up of studies that were carried out by psychologists who made the decision to center their attention on political concerns for the goal of conducting their research. An illustration of this may be seen in the research that Ajzen and Fishbein (1980) conducted on the concept of justifiable action, which will be further upon in the following paragraphs.

Keywords: *Social Psychology, Social Psychology and Politics, Social Psychology and Politics, Politics and Sociology, Politics and Psychology, Political Sociology, Political Psychology*

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Introduction

During the process of putting their ideas into reality, one of the areas that they concentrated on was the voting behavior of individuals. Both Ajzen and Fishbein have said that it was not their purpose to attempt to explain political happenings on their own. They were able to put their theories to the test in a variety of settings, politics being only one of those settings. Because of this, the work they have done is an excellent illustration of the second group of psychological theories that may be applied to politics, despite the fact that their major concentration is not on particularly comprehending political occurrences. The third kind of study in political science is made up of studies that concentrate on political happenings but may be applied to settings outside than politics. A great illustration of this idea may be found in the research that has been done on motivated reasoning in politics. According to Taber and Lodge (2006), motivated reasoning in politics shows that people combine newly obtained information with current opinions. Despite the fact that the theory is centered on political concerns, the psychological processes that it explains are present in a variety of life domains than politics. The fourth branch of research that falls under the umbrella of political psychology is known as "really" political research. Because of this categorization, it is clear that the research investigates solely political topics, and the conclusions cannot be understood with regard to any other context.

Methodology

The investigation of the connection that exists between ideologies and values is a significant addition to this discipline. Ideological adjectives such as "left" and "right" are examples of concepts that have their origins in politics. The fact that this is the case shows that political psychology is more than just the application of general psychological concepts to the study of politics. In addition, the study of political psychology has a primary and particular emphasis on the creation of ideas that are directed toward the examination of political problems. Following that, we will discuss how research in the second, third, and fourth categories contributes to our understanding of political leadership, voting behavior, and ideology. We have decided not to put

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research in the first category since there is already an excessive amount of material to cover, and the work itself is not concerned with politics.

Compilation from the Literature

Leadership in Politics

There have been several times throughout history in which individual political leaders have made important contributions. There is a lot of evidence to suggest that things would be different if other people were in charge, despite the fact that it is impossible to know for definite what would take place if other people were in charge. This is the case, despite the fact that it is impossible to know with absolute certainty what will take place. The role that Mikhail Gorbachev played in the rehabilitation of the Soviet Union serves as an excellent illustration of this principle. As a direct consequence of his efforts, the Cold War came to an end and the communist regime was overthrown. His personality was most likely one of the many factors that went into the formation of glasnost and perestroika policies, which encompassed both economic and governmental changes. These policies were implemented in the Soviet Union. It is logical to suppose that he is less connected to the expectations of others, more ready to take chances, and more open to experiencing new things. In light of this, a number of questions and issues have arisen, some of which include how the personalities of political leaders should be understood, how their personalities should be assessed, and when and how a leader's personality impacts conduct while they are in office. When questions of this kind are addressed, the insights that are acquired may be able to assist in the selection of the most capable leaders.

These issues have consistently been seen as having a significant amount of significance within the realm of political psychology. Although many other psychological aspects of leadership, such as physical attractiveness, height, and the influence of birth order, have been explored, it is clear that the aspect of a leader's personality is the most intriguing for academics to study. Personality factors known as the "Big Five" Let's begin with the kind of research that takes a more theoretical approach to the discipline of psychology and applies it to the realm of politics.

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Research on political leaders may be handled from a wide variety of perspectives; one example of this is the application of general theories of personality to particular public figures. In comparison to the other personality theories, the one that has become the most widely accepted is the five-component trait model, which is also referred to as the Big Five on occasion. This model of personality identifies five major qualities, including neuroticism (also known as emotional stability), extroversion (often known as liveliness), agreeableness (also known as friendliness), and openness to new experiences. Each of these characteristics is discussed in more detail below. The fifth essential quality is one's level of conscientiousness. According to studies conducted on both the general public and the political elite, political orientation has been shown to have a continuous correlation with both of these traits. For instance, according to the results of the research carried out by Dietrich et al. (2012) on state lawmakers in the United States, openness to new experiences is positively related with liberalism, but conscientiousness is significantly connected with conservatism. This was shown in the study on state legislators in the United States. It is standard practice in the area of psychology to analyze people's personalities by having them complete questionnaires intended to evaluate such characteristics. This kind of investigation is called personality profiling. Personal accounts, on the other hand, are not the most reliable source when it comes to doing an in-depth analysis of the personalities of political leaders. In most cases, the space allowed in survey questionnaires that are delivered to political elite only permits a limited number of questions to be asked, and response rates are often relatively low. It is very evident that this method is not nearly as well suited to determining the personalities of former political leaders who have passed away, which is normally the focus of study. This is due to the fact that study interests often center on deceased political figures after they have passed away. As a direct consequence of this, you will be need to use several tactics. Having other individuals fill out the questionnaires 'on behalf of' the politician in issue is one potential solution to the problem. The research carried out by Rubenzer, Faschingbauer, and Ones (2004) was carried out in this manner. They accomplished this by grading the personalities of all of the United States presidents based on the judgments of biographers and other individuals who had worked closely with or had substantial experience with the presidents in question. Rubenzer et al. (2004) explored if there was a link between the trait scores of presidents and how effectively they did their jobs (based on the judgments of notable historians). After determining the personalities of all of the presidents, the

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researchers looked to see whether there was a connection between the two. Successful presidents had considerably greater levels of openness, extroversion, and neuroticism, but significantly lower levels of agreeableness, as compared to presidents who were just average. Presidents Thomas Jefferson and Abraham Lincoln stand out as especially notable examples due to their roles in their respective fields. The second finding, which is at least as significant as the first, is that the general correlations are poor, and the vast majority of personality characteristics do not correspond with levels of perceived intelligence. This finding is at least as significant as the finding that the general correlations are weak. Investigating the histories of prominent political figures, the study of political leadership often makes use of content analysis as one of its many different methodologies. Some of the researchers employed content analysis to concentrate their attention on the biographical information, namely the sections that were connected to the characteristics of the subject's personality. Content analysis was the methodology used by other researchers in their investigations of interviews and speeches. Even if they were not written wholly by the political leaders themselves, they are still able to properly reflect the qualities of the political leaders because the political leaders themselves pick the speechwriters, the speechwriters 'know' their clients, and the political leaders constantly modify the drafts. Even if they were not written entirely by the political leaders themselves, they are still able to adequately represent the qualifications of the political leaders. The traits of political leaders are correctly reflected in these, even if they were not wholly penned by the political leaders themselves. One of these academics is Winter (1987), who presents the theory that the efficacy of political leaders is tied to the degree to which their personalities and the requirements of society at any particular period complement each other. Winter's study was published in 1987. Winter arranged the keynote addresses given by American presidents into categories according to their motives. These categories included reasons for success, reasons for commitment, and reasons for power. Examining cultural materials such as well-known novels or reading books written for children, on the other hand, was an effective way to get insight into the requirements of the culture. Winter investigated how the motivational profiles of presidential candidates' impact both their level of popularity (as judged by the candidate's margin of election win) and their level of perceived size (as evaluated by the ratings given to the candidate by historians). He came to the conclusion that the degree to which a president's motivation scores mirrored those of society at the time indicated the president's level

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of popularity, but the performance of a president was always determined by the traits of the leader, such as power motivation, regardless of the circumstances.

While earlier research focused on characteristics and their underlying causes, most recent research has taken a more cognitive tack. An operational code is a collection of views that a leader has about the world, such as whether peace or conflict is at the center of political life, if the future is predictable and controllable, and how it can be controlled. The notion of an operational code is related to this set of beliefs. The most effective means are available for accomplishing political aims. It is a widely held belief that ideas of this kind have the potential to significantly influence political conduct. For instance, a study of Russian President Vladimir Putin's operating guidelines came to the conclusion that Putin is less likely to react emotionally or impulsively, that he would respond to "bad" conduct as well as "excellent" performance, and that collaboration will suffer (Dyson, 2001). The vast bulk of research conducted on political leadership and personality traits has concentrated its emphasis on heads of authoritarian regimes and presidents of the United States of America (including Nazi Germany, the Soviet Union, and Iraq). The research that Kaarbo and Hermann carried out in 1998 is an example of an exception to this norm. They analyzed the diverse approaches of management used by the following prime ministers from various European nations:

German chancellors Konrad Adenauer (1949–1963) and Helmut Kohl (1982–1998), as well as British prime ministers Margaret Thatcher (1979–1990) and John Major (1990–1997).

They coded nearly one hundred press conferences and parliamentary question sessions into five characteristics: conceptual complexity (openness to knowledge), belief in one's ability to control what is happening, need for power, need for commitment, and task orientation (for example, focusing on solving problems and completing tasks rather than maintaining good relationships.) is important. This profile reveals that it has produced profiles that incorporate features such as personalities, motives, cognitive orientations, and behavioral inclinations. This collection of characteristics is the product of various research on political leadership. The analysis of political leaders often makes use of these profiles.

Findings

The very first thing that became clear from this investigation was that each of the four managers used their own one-of-a-kind strategy when it came to running the company. They have formed themselves rather than having their political setting mold them, and they have used the possibilities they have had to exert influence. Adenauer and Thatcher were both crusaders who seized power and controlled the political system in their respective countries. They saw any political constraint as an annoyance rather than as something that may limit the acts they could do, and they did not respect it. In politics, timing is key, and how important it is Karabo often influenced by the specifics of the situation in which a choice will be taken. Kohl is more of a strategist than a politician. The Major was more grounded in reality, and he picked up cues from his environment about what actions needed to be taken. It was crucial to him to assemble a group of influential individuals around him who could provide a unified viewpoint that would either assist in finding a solution to the issue at hand or help manage the situation. He was especially focused on making progress toward the first objective. (Kaarbo and Hermann, 1998, page 256) [Kaarbo and Hermann] Kaarbo and Hermann conducted research to determine if the style of leadership had an effect on the development of foreign policy. They observed that the Crusaders were more likely to participate in risky behaviors and actively sought out confrontation in the global arena. That was the same thing that they observed. An excellent illustration of this phenomenon is the decision that Margaret Thatcher made in 1982 to launch a military operation in response to Argentina's invasion of the Falkland Islands (often referred to as Malvinas). Making choices under an emergency situation When there is a crisis, it is logical to think that having strong political leadership is the most crucial thing. The answer that Margaret Thatcher gave to the invasion of the Falkland Islands is illustrative of how the personality of a leader may affect decision-making in the midst of an emergency situation. However, a person's personality is not the only factor that should be considered when selecting a leader. The decisions that are made by political leaders almost never occur in a vacuum. To begin, the feelings of the general populace might have an effect on the choices made by political leaders. This can happen for a number of reasons. Second, individuals who have political power do not bear entire responsibility for the

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decisions that are made. It is not uncommon to have ministers, civilian staff, political consultants, and even military advisers in close proximity to leaders of state, such as presidents and prime ministers. Therefore, in order for us to comprehend how political leaders come to conclusions during times of crisis, we first need to comprehend the manners in which political leaders communicate with the general public and the group dynamics in which political leaders take part. It is simpler to generate support for aggressive acts, as shown by research on crisis decision-making and the effect of public opinion. On the other hand, it is more difficult to garner support for conciliatory activities. This study series has provided us with a number of valuable lessons, but this one stands above the others. Consequently, decision makers put themselves in more risk at home if they resort to a solution that involves reconciliation and reconciliation rather than continuing in a conflict situation. This is because staying in a conflict scenario is more likely to culminate in violence. In 1979, Kahneman and Tversky were the ones who came up with the concept of prospect theory. It is one of the theories that may help us understand why this is the case, and it comes from the fields of economics and psychology. It is clear that the anticipated utility theory may be given an answer by referring to this specific theory. The potential costs and benefits of each of the many possibilities are given a multiplier based on the likelihood that the anticipated utility theory will take them into account. The alternative that offers the "highest utility" to users is the one that will be chosen. According to prospect theory, actions diverge from anticipated benefit when decision makers fear loss and the amount of risk is in the moderate to high range. As a result, the decision maker is willing to incur greater risk in order to limit prospective losses (for more detail on this topic, see to Chapter 7).

Argument

Studies in international relations have made available a number of possibilities for putting this idea to the test and verifying it. Loss aversion is driving political leaders to choose positions that are more divisive than they usually would. mainly due to the fact that political leaders who engage in reconciliatory behavior run the risk of losing the favor of the general population. Other study has revealed that judgments made during times of crisis may not necessarily rely on expected

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utility models generated from economic theory. Prospect theory can assist explain the disparities that have been found in this research.

Groupthink

Not only are political leaders impacted by the viewpoints of the general population, but also by the perspectives of the individuals they surround themselves with. It is possible to make the case that the theory of groupthink that was presented by Janis (1972) is the most significant theory with relation to political leadership and activities involving groups of people. He analyzed many significant political events, such as the invasion of the Bay of Pigs and the assault on Pearl Harbor, in which the government of the United States seems to have made poor choices (the escalation of the Vietnam War). Janis came to the conclusion that knowing group processes is essential to comprehending bad decision-making. Subsequent study that was based on fresh facts about these options indicated that Janis overestimated some of the effects that may occur under these conditions. Additionally, this research demonstrated that individual leadership styles are also a factor in the process of decision making. According to the groupthink theory, the decisions that may not be in anyone's best interest when made by relatively small groups of individuals in certain contexts may be the result of groupthink. These factors include a dedication to the in-group, isolation from influences from the outside, leadership that places an emphasis on direction, and stress. Janis (1972) has identified a variety of inconsistencies in the way decisions are made as a consequence of these defects.

First, initial judgments will not be subjected to a full evaluation on the basis of fresh evaluations, and group discussions will be restricted to a limited number of possibilities (often only two). Second, pertinent information from pertinent specialists is not actively obtained, and the information that supports initial findings is given the highest weight, rather than assessing information on the merits of the information on its own rather than analyzing information on its own merits. Third, the potential challenges that may arise throughout the process of putting the election into effect are not taken into consideration. When seen as a whole, these processes create an atmosphere in which bad decision-making is at the very least more common, if not the norm,

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than it should be. Furthermore, it is clearly more likely than the citizens of the nation in question might anticipate given the circumstances in which they live. It is interesting to notice that the psychological processes that are related with groupthink are the exact reverse of what we have observed in the past about the personality attributes that lead to greatness in presidents. This is something that is worth noting. It was found that openness, more than any other personality quality, was the most important factor in a successful presidential candidate. And precisely what is lacking in groupthink is receptivity to brand new ideas. From the findings that Janis (1972) uncovered, there are at least one or two significant inferences that may be derived. To get things started, it would be a good idea to urge those outside of the ingroup as well as members of the ingroup to challenge commonly held opinions.

Second, after an initial agreement has been achieved, it makes perfect sense to conduct what is known as a "second-round debate." This is because the original discussion likely led to the formation of the initial consensus. Alfred Sloan, a former president of General Motors, made the following observation during a business meeting that was referenced several times and gave a fascinating illustration of this insight: "Guys, I think we're all totally in agreement on this one." If this is the case, then I propose that we postpone further discussion of this problem until our next meeting, in order to allow ourselves time to develop conflicts and possibly get some insight into what the election is all about. I urge that we do this because: 1. Even though it goes against common sense, politicians who follow this plan have a greater chance of becoming good leaders. This is despite the fact that following this method goes against common sense. Electoral behavior Voting in elections provides individuals with the option to pick who will serve as their representative in government, making it one of the most essential everyday political activities that individuals may participate in.

Try as we may, we just can't seem to get a handle on why people vote the way they do, and this remains one of the most pressing questions in the area of political psychology. It's possible that the results of the selection research may have significant ramifications. It is fair to suppose that people have the capability to perform a broad variety of tasks if the study demonstrates that folks have high levels of education and pay attentive attention to policy. On the other hand, if it turns out that voters are poorly informed and pick candidates more or less randomly or, for

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example, on the basis of the candidates' physical appearance, then one may be more pessimistic about the possibility of an efficient democratic administration. Because of this, one will have less reason to be positive about the possibilities of democratic government being effective. Should you vote or not? That is the question.

Many people, including politicians and political scientists, have emphasized how essential it is for democracy to have a large number of persons actively engage in elections (Figure 15.3). This is considered to be one of the most crucial aspects of democracy. There is an opinion held by some that one of the most essential characteristics of democratic governance is high levels of citizen engagement. Others argue that the reasons people refrain and the sorts of citizens who abstain more than others are the two most important factors in determining whether or not abstentions contradict the democratic ideal. The primary issue has been that persons who are less well-off have a lower likelihood of voting, and as a consequence, their interests are not taken as seriously by politicians as are the interests of individuals who vote (or give). This would run counter to the fundamental principle of democracy, which holds that individuals should have about the same degree of influence as one another.

A large number of people casting their votes might help lessen the potentially disastrous effects. Researchers in social psychology, political science, and economics have all researched the elements that impact a person's decision to vote or not vote in an election. These researchers have found that there are a variety of factors that play a role in this decision. There are a number of factors that pique the attention of economists in this subject: To begin, the voting behavior of individuals presents a considerable obstacle for the rational choice theory. According to this argument, voters won't bother voting because they believe that their single vote has absolutely little possibility of making a difference, and as a result, they won't bother casting their ballots. However, in actuality, a significant number of individuals cast their ballots.

The psychological technique was contrasted with the economic approach by Quattrone and Tversky (1988), who came to the conclusion that the psychological method provides a much better understanding of the elements that influence voting decision. This is due to the fact that voters do not base their voting choices on the value that was calculated. People think that voting is part of their civic obligation, which is the primary reason why there are so many people showing up at

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the polls on election day. The act of voting is not done so much out of a desire to have an effect on the result of the election as it is due to the fact that there are societal norms in place. Accordingly, the option of whether or not to vote is an excellent example of an activity that is poorly understood on the basis of economic decision-making models. Social psychologists may contribute to an understanding of this choice by casting light on it, and they can also contribute to a knowledge of how economic decision-making models work. It should not come as a surprise that scholars have investigated a variety of various strategies to boost voter participation given the significance that is put on participation in election processes.

A good illustration of this would be a field experiment that investigated the impact of making personal pleas to voters in the last days before an election. This is the technique that several organizations, including governments, have chosen to use. However, the results of current investigations indicate that the efficacy of such therapies is to a limited extent.

Reasoned Action Theory

Let's shift our attention now to the choices that are made by the people who actually make use of their right to vote. What drives individuals to support a specific political party or candidate, and how can we better understand those drivers? The use of broad psychological theories and the usage of concepts that are significant in social psychology may be a useful approach that can be utilized to provide a solution for this problem. (McGuire, 1985) finds that only a small minority of social psychologists disagree with the assumption that attitudes are an essential concept. What could be more essential to who you are than the things that you love and the things that you despise? Additionally, a person's preferences, both good and bad, have a substantial impact on the decisions he makes. This applies to both the positive and the negative preferences.

Ajzen and Fishbein (1980) presented the most influential theory of attitudes and behaviors, and it was developed by these two researchers. This idea is known as the theory of reasoned action, and a variant of it that is somewhat modified is known as the theory of planned conduct (for additional information, see Chapter 2 of this book). According to the theory of reasoned action, the element that directly influences whether or not a specific conduct will be executed is the

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intention to perform that behavior. The formulation of an individual's intention for his future conduct is influenced by a number of factors, including the individual's degree of conformance with subjective norms and his assessment of the potential repercussions that may result from his actions.

In-depth new knowledge has been unearthed as a direct result of the application of attitude-behavior models to the voting process. For instance, the disparity between attitudes toward objects (parties) and attitudes toward conduct (voting for those parties) offers a perfect context for the practice of "strategic voting," which entails voting for a party that is not one's favorite party because it is one's favorite party. Another example would be voting for a candidate who is not one's favorite person. On the other hand, attitude-behavior models have not had a significant influence on the vast bulk of traditional election research. It has not been possible to persuade election experts of the validity of the idea that voters support particular politicians in the mistaken assumption that their political party would boost the candidate's chances of being elected to power. These kinds of findings are regarded as being tautological. In addition, theories like the theory of reasoned action do not identify which beliefs impact attitudes toward parties and candidates (for instance, views about the health of the economy, policy stances, or personal character), nor do they explain why beliefs are reviewed. This means that theories like the theory of reasoned action do not provide an answer to the question of how beliefs are evaluated. (For example, why is one person in favor of tax cuts and another against it?). As a consequence of this, attitude-behavior models are unable to provide responses to the kind of problems that election researchers are interested in addressing.

There is a distinction to be made between the notion of partisan attitude and the idea of attitude, which is often utilized in the area of social psychology. In a basic sense, attitudes are conceived of as positions on a single dimension ranging from highly positive to extremely negative; it is about whether specific aspects are positive or negative (for a more thorough take on the issue, see McGuire, 1985). Partisan perspectives include attitudes that may range from being very favorable to the Republican party to being extremely favorable to the Democratic party. The United States of America are being referred to here. In addition, the political viewpoints that were found were not believed to be an accurate representation of the voter's state of mind. This

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distinction was made only for the sake of analysis, with the intention of making it feasible to evaluate the influence of a variety of factors, including candidate pictures and highlighted themes (Figure 15.7). As a consequence of this, the explanation of voting behavior provided by the Michigan model is seen as being psychological. This is due to the fact that it is based on the knowledge that voters already have in their minds. On the other hand, it is neither extremely psychological in the sense that it represents specific mental processes that underlie voting, nor is it psychological in the sense that the concepts utilized are psychological entities. Rather, it is not psychological in any of these ways. Many individuals have found newfound inspiration because to the studies on voting that Campbell and his colleagues have been doing. Comparable studies have been carried out in nations outside of the United States, mostly in Western Europe. These studies are based on the results of national election surveys. The United Kingdom, Norway, Sweden, Denmark, Germany, and the Netherlands are all included in this group of nations. In some instances, academics in these nations were enthusiastic about the explanatory power of the Michigan model, while in other instances, academics in these countries expressed skepticism over the utility of the Michigan model outside of the United States (Thomassen and Rosema, 2009). One of the challenges is that it is difficult to put the measures into effect in political systems with several parties. On the other hand, the most crucial concerns concern the concept of party identity. It may be difficult to differentiate party identification and vote preference in certain nations, and the supposed consistency of party identity has been called into doubt. Because of this, when the Michigan model is used in Europe, it is hard to differentiate between long-term and short-term impacts; as a consequence, the theory loses some of its appeal. This demonstrates that it is not always feasible to successfully adapt concepts developed in one environment to another one in the same manner. Reasoning that is motivated politically by offering an explanation for the reliability of voter behavior, the voting model developed in Michigan provides a significant addition to the field. This is a significant addition to the discussion. The notion of motivational political reasoning has given researchers further insight into the fundamental psychological process. According to Taber and Lodge (2006), this theory describes how emotions and thoughts interact with one another and lead to biased information processing. Understanding the underlying psychological process via the lens of motivational political reasoning provides more insight. To be more explicit, when a person is provided with new knowledge, a sequence of automatic brain

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processes occurs in that individual's brain. People begin by organizing newly acquired information according to what they already know by using this framework. According to the hot cognition hypothesis, each and every concept that a person has had in the past has an emotional charge and is stored in their long-term memory in this manner. Both good and negative emotions might be experienced by the person as a direct consequence of the categorization process that takes place. The "hot cognitions" are what are responsible for driving the processing of incoming information, in accordance with the notion of motivated thinking. As a result, the process through which one's pre-existing attitudes impact their interpretation of freshly obtained knowledge is the most appropriate method to define motivated thinking. Taber and Lodge (2006) discovered three distinct mechanisms that lead to the biased processing of recently obtained data. Even if people have a propensity to accept information that is congruent with their pre-existing ideas without questioning whether or not it is accurate, the disapproval bias makes the assumption that individuals make more efforts to develop counter-arguments.

people are more prone to seek information that confirms and is consistent with their present views, as opposed to information that refutes their current attitudes, according to the hypothesis of confirmation bias. This is because people are more likely to seek information that confirms and is consistent with their beliefs. According to the previous attitude effect, persons who have strong ideas have a tendency to regard arguments that are compatible with their views as being more powerful and convincing. The combination of these three different systems is what produces motivational thinking in people, which in turn leads their emotions to become more exacerbated. This polarization in opinions is so powerful that it happens even when people are given comments favoring and opposing a certain point of view with equal weighting. Voters are only able to alter their judgements to reflect new knowledge in very unusual circumstances, such as when material that consistently and clearly contradicts previously held ideas is supplied to voters on a regular basis.

A good illustration of the ways in which political psychologists may contribute to and improve social psychological theories is provided by the idea of motivating reasoning. The concept of motivating political reasoning is extensible to a wide range of various areas of research and may be used in a number of contexts. For instance, these processes could explain why people continue

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to be loyal to their preferred brand even when they are presented with bad information about the business.

Ideology

It is customary to focus only on political points of view while doing research. While the focus of the study conducted by some researchers is on the assessment of political candidates, the focus of the research conducted by other researchers is on racial sentiment. Some individuals are curious about other people's perspectives on the topic of the death sentence, while others are interested in hearing other's perspectives on many elements of government policy. On the other hand, one may make the reasonable assumption that all of these political attitudes are at least related in some way. In the subject of political psychology, one of the most significant issues that is posed is "in what form and to what extent do such correlations exist?" The question that is being addressed is "in what form and to what extent do such correlations exist?" Exists a pattern of coherence in the way that people's perspectives on politics are arranged, for instance in terms of ideological leanings to the left, and right? Whether or whether the ideological orientations of public opinion have changed over the course of time and, if they have, the manner in which these shifts have happened (for instance, has the standard of living of people in Europe improved) are other issues that are the topic of passionate dispute. Right-wing throughout the course of the last two decades?) It is essential to consider if the idea is still influential in today's society. Exists (still) there anything that can be referred to as ideology? In his fundamental research, Converse (1964) said that attitudes towards different issues should be anticipated to be connected, and this assumption is realistic. Converse's study found that attitudes towards various problems were interrelated. The individual's fundamental ideological viewpoint is the primary factor that affects the degree to which there is a gap between their perspectives on certain subjects. For instance, one may assume that a person who is deemed liberal with regard to one topic will also be liberal with regard to another topic. However, real study conducted by Converse (1964) indicated that only approximately 10 percent of American voters arrange their opinions using ideological notions such as liberalism and conservatism or capitalism and socialism.

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The inconsistency in attitude had unfavorable effects, which were at least partially caused to by flaws in the research methods. For instance, the degree of link established between party identification and policy preferences has been shown to be poor in certain research. This is due to the fact that these two aspects are investigated in quite different methods. When the researchers explored both concepts using the same methodologies, they saw a considerable improvement in the correlation between the two. In addition, while the number of voters who are knowledgeable about each and every topic is quite low, the number of voters who are somewhat knowledgeable about at least some of the topics is very high. In more recent times, fresh material has surfaced that sheds light on the origin and importance of ideological divisions.

According to Funk et al. (2013), researchers in the fields of psychology and political science have found evidence indicating that there are significant and fundamental differences between liberals and conservatives. These scholars used a diverse range of methodologies, drawn from a number of academic subfields. Within the context of one of the trials, the participants were required to either generate a motor response or refrain from generating one. It has been shown that liberals and conservatives have distinct patterns of neurocognitive functioning overall: When they were made to repress their motor reflexes, liberals' brains showed greater levels of activity than conservatives' brains did. Others have demonstrated that political viewpoints are connected with physiological characteristics; as a consequence, conservatives are more likely than liberals to display greater levels of physiological reactivity in reaction to potentially harmful stimuli. This association between political viewpoints and physiological characteristics has led researchers to conclude that conservatives are more prone to feel fearful. The most recent events offer proof that ideas are still there and thriving. Considering how deeply ideologies are ingrained, one could wonder whether they will ever be destroyed completely.

Philosophy and core values There is an undeniable link between the study of ideology and the notion of socio-psychological values; despite the fact that socio-psychological values are only seldom discussed in these types of research. Rokeach's (1973) work in the realm of values is perhaps the most significant of all of these studies. Establishing the fundamental concepts that are common to all human civilizations was the goal of this endeavor. The value orientations of

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individuals were determined by asking them to choose, from a list of values, the value that, according to their own criteria, should be prioritized the most highly. During the course of his argument, Rokeach said that equality and freedom, two of the concepts that were specified, had significant ties to the ideology of the left and the right. In conjunction with the focus placed on equality (low vs. high) and the emphasis placed on freedom (low vs. high), this results in the creation of a two-dimensional space consisting of four categories that correspond to four distinct ideologies. These classifications include socialism (characterized by high equality and high freedom), communism (characterized by high equality but low freedom), capitalism (characterized by low equality but high freedom), and fascism (characterized by low equality but low freedom). According to Rokeach, the word "ideology" becomes one-dimensional when practically all members of a community lay a great emphasis on one of the two principles. He stated that this makes ideology a meaningless concept. This is consistent with the prevalent idea of ideology in today's culture, which is that the far left and far right (in Europe) or liberal and conservative (in the United States) exist on a continuum with poles at each end. In addition, the concept of values is a significant factor in the study that was conducted by Inglehart (1997) on materialism and post materialism. According to Inglehart, generational conflicts do not evolve (solely) over the right/left dichotomy, but also in terms of 'materialism' and 'post materialism'. He put up the hypothesis that the degree to which a person attaches significance to a specific value would be dependent, among other things, on the degree to which the goods that are essential to fulfill one's requirements are in short supply. items that are common and easy to get will not be regarded as highly as items that are less common, but they may fit needs that are presently unfilled. Maslow's theory indicated that needs may be ranked as a hierarchy, and that individuals would attempt to satisfy particular desires only if they have at least partly met more fundamental needs. It is not difficult to understand that Inglehart was affected by Maslow's theory, and it is obvious that Inglehart was impacted by Maslow's theory. It cannot be denied that Maslow's theory had a significant role in Inglehart's line of research. Inglehart made the observation that a person's fundamental characteristics are formed throughout childhood and adolescence, and that these characteristics will carry into maturity the value hierarchy that he developed. Inglehart (1997) developed the hypothesis that individuals of various generations had distinct approaches to valuing different things, and he based his reasoning on these ideas. Those who come of age during periods

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of economic instability have a more acute need to provide for their basic requirements, such as safety and financial stability. To characterize the ideas that younger generations put a relatively high importance on, Inglehart came up with the word "postmaterialist" to use. In contrast to avoiding price hikes and preserving order, these principles place a greater emphasis on individuals' rights to freedom of speech and active involvement in decision-making processes. According to Inglehart, this shift in generations will be mirrored in varied levels of support for various political parties and views.

In point of fact, empirical study has shown that there are shifts in the value orientations of various generations throughout the course of human history. In addition, there is a connection between one's value orientations and their political inclinations as well as their voting preference. Green parties serve as an excellent example since they have the backing of a sizeable proportion of individuals who place a high importance on postmaterialist concepts. The conclusions reached by Inglehart were not taken as given without being questioned. Numerous investigations have led researchers to the conclusion that Inglehart's concept of value change does not adequately capture all of the factors that go into it. In addition, the chasm that exists between post materialism and materialism has not grown as much as the divide that exists between the political left and the political right. Concerns over subsequent ideological positions remained an incredibly crucial factor in the process of comprehending political action.

Conclusion

Prejudice is sometimes referred to as "bias" because of the significant influence that ideological orientations play in the phenomenon. This is particularly the case when it comes to the particular political theory known as authoritarianism on the right (Stenner, 2005). According to Sidanius and Pratto (1999), a further crucial measure connected with prejudice is referred to as social dominance orientation. This aspect of prejudice deals with the question of whether a person wants interactions between the ingroup and the outgroup to be equal or hierarchical. The tendency

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for hierarchical connections between the ingroup and the outgroup is one of the hallmarks of the phenomenon known as bias. According to Duckitt (2006), both scales are better suited for evaluating ideological belief components associated with conservatism (see also Jost, Glaser, Kruglanski, and Sulloway, 2003). Duckitt's argument may be found in Jost, Glaser, Kruglanski, and Sulloway's study. He maintained that although while right-wing authoritarianism and social dominance orientation were generally considered as personality factors, both scales were seen as more suited for assessing ideological belief dimensions. This was despite the fact that both were first seen as being personality variables. In contrast to the tie that exists between social conservatism and authoritarianism on the right, the connection that exists between social dominance orientation and economic conservatism is far more intimate. The social dominance orientation is a reaction to the belief that the world is a 'forest of brutal struggle' where the strong win and the weak lose. Authoritarianism is a response to the view that the world is hazardous, unpredictable, and menacing. Duckitt found that both perspectives are grounded in one of two distinct worldviews. In addition to this, he maintained that these worldviews are formed not just by the circumstances of society but also by the personality of the person. For instance, being confronted with a threat will induce one to believe that the world is a dangerous place, which would ultimately culminate in authoritarianism. This offers an explanation for why measures of authoritarianism and social dominance orientation are vulnerable to threat manipulations in tests and experiments. Therefore, residents in densely populated areas in the United States who regard the world as a hazardous place are more likely to have an unfavorable attitude of immigrants than those who do not live in such an area. This is particularly the case if you reside in a community that has a large concentration of immigrant residents. Those who wish to battle prejudices using treatment techniques based on social psychology have reason to be hopeful since social settings can be altered more readily than personality qualities. In light of this, those who want to use social psychology-based therapy methods to combat biases have reason to be optimistic.

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